

Deep learning algorithms for delaminations identification on composite panels by wave propagation signal analysis

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ABSTRACT

Performances are a key concern in aerospace vehicles, requiring safer structures with as little consumption as possible. Composite materials replaced aluminum alloys even in primary structures to achieve higher performances with lighter components. However, random events such as low-velocity impacts may induce damages that are typically more dangerous and mostly not visible than in metals. Structural Health Monitoring deals mainly with sensorised structures providing signals related to their “health status” aiming at lower maintenance costs and weights of aircrafts. Much effort has been spent during last years on analysis techniques for evaluating metrics correlated to damages’ existence, location and extensions from signals provided by the sensors networks. Deep learning techniques can be a very powerful instrument for signals patterns reconstruction and selection but require the availability of consistent amount of both healthy and damaged structural configuration experimental data sets, with high materials and testing costs, or data reproduced by validated numerical simulations. Within this work will be presented two supervised deep neural networks trained by experimental measurements as well as numerically generated strain propagation signals. The final scope is the detection of delaminations into composites plates for aerospace employ. The first type is based directly on the processing trough a convolutional autoencoder of the rough signals of both healthy and damaged structural configurations. The second approach is instead based on the production of images trough signal processing techniques and on employ of an image recognition convolutional network. Both networks are trained and tested on combinations of experimental and numerical data.

Keywords: composite structures, structural health monitoring, deep neural networks, unsupervised and supervised deep learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Last developments in the modern aerospace industry push towards an improvement in flight efficiency and autonomy leading to a great increment in the usage of composite materials. They allow to lower the weight and obtain easily more complex shapes, but, due to their peculiar composition and fabrication methods, they are affected by delaminations and defects. So, every aircraft’s component is subject to time-scheduled maintenance sessions even when there is no clear evidence that it is required. This is a very expensive and time consuming process.

In this field, the Structural Health Monitoring technology (SHM system) [1,2,3,4,5], based on networks of distributed sensors embedded, or secondary bonded, throughout the whole structure under investigation, could be conveniently used for real-time health monitoring and/or as a data acquisition tool. Structural data, however, may constitute an enormous amount of information that in most cases is difficult to classify. Furthermore, since time is an important factor, the automation of the analysis process could be a significant advantage in this field. From this point of view, intelligent algorithms that can take decision in an autonomous manner reducing the human participation, like Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), may be useful to overcome this impasse.

Structural data may be adequately filtered with the aid of specific Deep Neural Networks designed and trained for the structural context and aimed to the classification and identification of significant parameters [6,7,8]. The DNNs, based on strategic engineering criteria, may represent an effective and efficient analysis tool to promote faster data analysis and classification. In the field of aircraft maintenance, this approach may lead, for example, to a faster awareness of a component health situation or predict failures. Neural Networks typically requires a relevant amount of data in order to be trained and to acquire the necessary reliability in classifying and recognizing the occurrence of the selected event but, once trained, they can be extremely effective and low-time consuming in analysing each single scenario to be classified. In this study the potentialities of deep learning with high frequency Lamb waves propagation based SHM methodologies are investigated employing explicit finite element simulations to collect propagation signals due to impact damages on a composite plate; this approach will also be employed in the next future to populate experimental data sets necessary for deep learning algorithm. Previous experimental signals acquired on the real impacted carbon fiber panel have been used to validate a numerical equivalent to allow the expansion of the dataset available [7].

Numerical time history signals have been collected for both the healthy and un-healthy state of the structure and transformed into RGB images. A well-known convolutional algorithm trained on healthy and damaged signals is used to identify anomalies in the form of delamination in the structure. The paper presents the pre-liminary results achieved by the authors.

2. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

The Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) represent a group of highly successful deep neural network architectures adopted in computer vision applications and in applications that process media such as audio and video. The most popular application of convolutional neural network is to identify, by a computer and with a certain probability, what an image represents [10]. Such networks are built to analyze images included within certain datasets and classify objects in the images within them. The basic structure of a convolutional neural network consists of a convolutional layer, a nonlinear activation function, a pooling layer, and a fully connected layer. A convolutional process applied to an image is equivalent to applying a filter to that image. Convolution is defined by an array called the kernel, which is generally smaller than the image, and is applied by translating the kernel to it. The result of the convolutional filter depends on the numerical content of the kernel matrix. Varying the convolutional kernels, it is possible to obtain an infinity of filters, which can highlight some characteristics of the image and hide others. Generally, a convolutional layer manages several kernels that are all applied to the same input image, so that it is possible to have many different filters.

Example of convolution

Convolution layer filters provide denser information, highlighting some features and eliminating others that would constitute noise. So, a pooling operation is applied to decrease the size of the input image, maintaining the main characteristics of the same.

The input image is scanned with the pooling matrix obtaining a submatrix containing the maximum value (Max pooling) and the average value (Average pooling) of all input elements. The result is not a simple resizing of the image because the maximum or average information is maintained.

3. SHM ALGORITHM IMPLEMENTATION

The goal of the work is to develop a neural network capable of detecting damage and its position in a composite panel exploiting Lamb waves. For this purpose, a numerical model was used to simulate the propagation of Lamb waves in a flat composite panel. Then, a Matlab algorithm has been created to transform the detected signals into images that the adopted neural network classifies as damaged or intact.

3.1 Numerical model and signal analysis

The composite panel considered consists of 12 plies of three different pre-preg types oriented according to multiple directions. Plies material characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Material	ρ	E_1	E_2	E_3	$G_{12} = G_{23} = G_{31}$
5harness	1.77 g cm^{-3}	65 000 MPa	65 000 MPa	8800 MPa	3600 MPa
Biaxial	1.79 g cm^{-3}	81 000 MPa	81 000 MPa	8800 MPa	4100 MPa
Uniaxial	1.79 g cm^{-3}	152 000 MPa	8800 MPa	8800 MPa	4100 MPa

Table 1 – material properties

The lamination sequence can be written as:

$$[5H(0^\circ/90^\circ), B(+45^\circ / -45^\circ), U(0^\circ/90^\circ), U(0^\circ/90^\circ), B(+45^\circ / -45^\circ), B(0^\circ/90^\circ)]_s$$

Where 5H ("5harness") is a particular biaxial fabric characterized by the overlapping of one warp thread every five weft (Fig. 1a) "B" stands for biaxial, "U" for uniaxial [7,8]. The PZT sensors, utilized for lamb waves generation and acquisition, are applied on the panel according to the geometry in Fig. 1b.

The "pitch-catch" technique has been adopted for signals acquisition and damage detection, that is, a transducer behaves as an actuator, while the remaining sensors detect the signal that has been released inside the panel. Four different positions were considered for impact damage simulation (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. a) 5-Harness Satin Weave Layer; b) composite panel sensors configuration

Fig. 2. a) damage position 1; b) damage position 2

The signals obtained will be affected by the influence of damage every time it is present. Of course, since wave propagation in composites is a complex mechanism, it is more convenient to compare the signals acquired with the ones from the undamaged model (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. a) damage position 3; b) damage position 4

A key point is the data analysis from rough signals to get a proper identification system. Features (time of flight, group velocity, signal transmission factor, wave energy) are extracted with an appropriate signal processing technique obtaining a diagnosis that presents location and/or severity of the damage.

Fig. 4. Signals comparison between pristine and damaged model (path 20_46)

So, if “ f ” is the particular propagation feature considered, it is possible to define a damage index according to the following formulation:

$$DI = \frac{(f_d - f_b) \cdot (f_d - f_b)}{f_b \cdot f_b}$$

Where f_d is the value obtained by the signal of the panel as it is at the analysis time, while f_b is the one extracted by the baseline propagation. Then, a damage index (DI) close to zero suggests a healthy-like propagation, while a value over a certain threshold warns for a failure. Statistical signal analyses allowed to establish that a DI below 0.072 means damage absence, while a DI above 1.26 is significant of a certain presence of damage. In this way, it is also possible to understand in the first approximation where the damage is located considering the most damaged paths. This approach is called "multi-path analysis" [5]. However, to correctly classify all possible propagation paths, it is also necessary to consider those having a DI value in the range 0.072 and 1.26 and, therefore, more difficult to classify. The purpose is not only to train the network to correctly classify all paths having a DI less than 0.072 or greater than 1.26, but also to verify how it behaves with propagation paths having an intermediate DI between these two values, considering that the paths close to the damage must be classified as "damaged" and those that away from the damage must be classified as "intact".

3.2 RGB images generation

To implement the convolutional approach, the acquired signals are transformed into RGB images exploiting a MATLAB code. RGB (Red Green Blue) is an additive color model, that is, an abstract mathematical model that allows to represent colors in numerical form, using the red, green, and blue color components [11]. These colors together determine a color

space that can be defined as a cube aligned with the Cartesian axes of a three-dimensional space, where the amount of red color is represented along the X-axis, the amount of green along the Y-axis, and the amount of blue along the Z-axis (Figure

Fig. 5) In this representation each possible color has a unique position. The maximum value that each of the three colors can take is 255, because the number of bits used to represent the color of each individual pixel is 24, that means 8 bits (one byte) for each color channel. Consequently, considering the byte definition, 256 (28) color levels are possible for each color component ranging from 0 to 255. When the three components assume maximum value (maximum intensity) the white color is obtained, while when the three components assume the value 0 (zero intensity) the black color is obtained.

Fig. 5. RGB model

Each image obtained concerns a specific actuator-sensor path and consists of the overlap between the signal detected in the intact panel and that detected in the damaged panel. Going from top to bottom, the signals overlap consists of 10 intact signals, 10 signals in which a damaged and an intact alternate, and finally 10 damaged signals. Once the image of the aligned signals has been obtained, the absolute maximum “M” is calculated. Then the RGB components (Red, Green, Blue) are calculated, making sure to associate with M the maximum intensity of white if positive or the maximum intensity of black if negative, while all the other values are obtained linearly from these two (Fig. 6). The result is an array in which each value is between 0 and 1. In this way, each pixel corresponds to a trio of (x, y, z) values, to which a specific color is associated, according to the position assumed in the color space of the RGB model. So, a total of 624 images have been obtained (156 for each damage), each one characterized by its own DI.

Fig. 6. RGB transformed signal.

3.3 Image analysis

For images analysis the Google Net neural network [12], already present in MATLAB, was used. It is a deep convolutional neural network architecture codenamed Inception that achieves the new state of the art for classification and detection in the ImageNet Large-Scale Visual Recognition Challenge 2014 (ILSVRC14); is a convolutional network consisting of 144 layers, which requires an image as input and returns its classification in output (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Google Net CNN

Starting with an initial dataset of 624 images, 269 healthy images ($DI < 0.072$) and 144 corrupted images ($DI > 1.26$) were identified. Among these, 90 images were causally chosen (45 intact and 45 damaged) to train the network to correctly classify the intact from the damaged ones. Another set of 10 images, 5 intact and 5 damaged, was used, instead, for validation. So, the 90% of the total images was used for training and the remaining 10% for validation (Figure 8).

The network training phase was carried out using MATLAB's Deep Network Designer, a tool that allows to graphically train a neural network, entering the appropriate training parameters such as learning speed, validation frequency and number of epochs.

Fig. 8. Images selected for training

After the training the network showed an accuracy of 100% (Fig. 9). At this point, the remaining 313 images with a DI less than 0.072 or greater than 1.26 were analyzed. The results were collected in an uncertainty matrix (Fig. 10).

Fig. 9. Training results

3.4 Confusion matrix

The confusion matrix allows the evaluation of the quality of a classification method comparing the “correct” result with the “predicted” one. Every cell of the matrix is associated to a real and to a calculated classification and reports the number or the percentage of instances in which the same situation repeats. Usually, rows and columns are ordered in such a way, that cells for which the two values coincide are on the diagonal. In the case of the classification matrices presented in this work, the top left cell reports the number of well-recognized undamaged signals, the bottom right one indicates the instances of damaged propagations correctly classified; on the top-right space it is indicated the number of times that a “pristine signal” is predicted to be damaged (false alarms), while in the bottom left one the instances of damaged propagations classified as “pristine”.

The network was tested both with pristine ($DI < 0.072$) and damaged ($DI > 1.26$) images, and with images having an intermediate DI. In particular, the latter analysis led to the definition of new DI thresholds.

	undamaged	219	0
Real Classification	undamaged	219	0
	damaged	0	94
	damaged	0	94
		undamaged	damaged
		Predicted Classification	

Fig. 10. Confusion matrix of images with a DI less than 0.072 or greater than 1.26

The accuracy degree of the classified images was particularly high. The image in Fig. 11, having a DI = 0.0035, was recognized as integral with a degree of accuracy equal to 99.9%. The image in Fig. 12, on the other hand, has a DI = 54.2415 and has been recognized as damaged with an accuracy level of 98.4%.

Fig. 11. Accuracy of undamaged image classification

Fig. 12. Accuracy of damaged image classification

3.5 Classification with $0.072 < DI < 1.26$

The analysis regarding images having a DI between 0.072 and 1.26 is more complex. It is not possible to say a priori if the image refers to an intact or to a damaged condition, but this mainly depends on the path of the wave to which it refers: if it is close to damage, then the image can be considered damaged, while if it is far from damage the image can be considered intact. However, there is no longer a marked difference, as before, between intact and damaged images that allows them to be easily distinguished (Fig. 13 and Fig. 14).

Fig. 13. Undamaged path image (path 44_20)

Fig. 14. Damaged path image (Path 44_46)

The analysis of images with a DI between 0.072 and 1.26 was limited only to the damage position 1 (Fig. 2a), to verify the behavior of the network and identify any critical issues. Starting from a dataset of 62 images, the following results were obtained (Fig. 15):

Real Classification	undamaged	36	6
	damaged	0	20
		undamaged	damaged
		Predicted Classification	

Fig. 15. Confusion matrix of images with a DI between 0.072 and 1.26

The network correctly classified 56 images out of 62. The remaining six were classified as damaged even if intact (Fig. 15), but with a low degree of accuracy (Fig. 16 to Fig. 18) indicating a greater uncertainty than in the previous case.

Fig. 16. Path 21_44 classification (actuator sensor 21)

Fig. 17. Path 49_43 classification (actuator sensor 49)

Fig. 18. Path 20_48 classification (actuator sensor 20)

The six images erroneously classified as damaged are equal to each other two by two since each pair of paths is made up of the direct path and its reciprocal in which the actuator and sensor are exchanged (path 21_44 and 44_21, path 49_43 and 43_49, path 20_48 and 48_20). The double wrong classification is justified by the Acoustic Reciprocity theorem since the signal detected by a sensor B after it has been emitted by a transducer A is the same as that detected by sensor A when it is released by transducer B.

Starting from the analysis of the images having a DI between 0.072 and 1.26, it was possible to identify two new threshold values for the DI: 0.4 and 0.9. All images with a DI less than 0.4 were considered undamaged, while those with a DI greater than 0.9 were considered damaged. A number of 407 intact and 168 damaged images were obtained, including the 100 images utilized for training. Using the recalibrated DI threshold values, the network was able to correctly recognize all the images, except for the, above discussed, 6 misclassified images (Figure 19).

	undamaged	351	6
Real Classification			
	damaged	0	118
		undamaged	damaged
		Predicted Classification	

Fig. 19. Confusion matrix of images with recalibrated DI threshold values

In this way the number of images having an intermediate DI has been considerably reduced and, at the same time, the network has continued to operate by correctly classifying almost all the intact images from the damaged ones. With the previous threshold values, the images with an intermediate DI were 211, in this case only 49. However, a further reduction of the amplitude between the DI thresholds would lead to a less reliable network.

4. NET TRAINING BY EXPERIMENTAL AND “HYBRID” SIGNALS

Once the effectiveness in signal classification was proofed for the chosen network, the real intent of the work was to verify the possibility of training the net by a hybrid combination of experimental and numerical data to classify experimental signals. In this case the numerical data would permit to “expand” the experimental data set, for example including more damage locations than the experimental damage scenario available (avoiding the damaging of more test articles in many locations). For these purposes the experimental signals data base presented in [7] has been combined to the previous numerical one: they both referred to the same test article sensorised with the same sensors networks. In detail the numerical wave propagation signals were obtained after validating and correlating the numerical model with the experimental data (See the activities presented in [7] for more details).

It has been deduced, from experiments on numerical data, that in order to identify the damage thresholds, a statistical investigation of the damage index of the images is necessary. The reference values found are 10 and 100; they are representative of a certain integrity of the signal if $DI < 10$ and of a certain damage if $DI > 100$. These values are much higher than the values found in the numerical models, as we expected, because the experimental signal always shows imperfections, unlike the numerical signal which is always “perfect” and identical for all the repetitions.

Fig. 20. Generic experimental image damaged (above) and intact (below)

As shown in Fig. 20, it is clear that the damaged images are characterized by a series of horizontal knurls. The latter are induced by disturbances in signal reception, attributable to damage. The tested panel was sensorised by an array of 13 PZT sensors, each one acting both as vibrations source and receiver alternately (see Fig 1.b); activating one PZT each time (multiplied by thirteen PZT) and letting the other twelve listening it was possible to acquire 156 signals. Three acquisition repetitions were performed for considering the unavoidable experimental variability of the acquired signals. Operating in this way, we obtained an overall number of 468 images of which 212 damaged images, 137 intact images and 119 images with intermediate DI (which were subjected to a subsequent analysis).

From the set of generated images, the images relating to the first repetition were filtered, for a total of 117 images (70 damaged images and 47 intact images). Furthermore, from the previous numerical experimentation, we have extrapolated a pattern consisting of 90 images, 45 intact and 45 damaged.

We trained the network in three different ways to evaluate the recognition efficiency of the experimental images and the relative reliability: numerical, experimental and hybrid training.

For numerical training, we used only numerical data, specifically 45 intact images and 45 damaged images. Furthermore, 10% of them were used for validation, which found 100% accuracy.

Fig. 21. Numerical training results

The goal of this training is to have a network capable of classifying the experimental images. As remarked before, digital signals and experimental signals are "by definition" different from each other, so we expect recognition to have little success in this case.

The experimental training was carried out by selecting, among the 117 images considered, 15 damaged images and 15 intact images.

Fig. 22. Experimental training results

Also on this occasion the accuracy of the validation reached 100%. Unlike the previous training, we expect the network trained with this type of pattern to work correctly because it must classify images that have an experimental origin and, therefore, consistent with that of the images used for training.

For the hybrid training, 30 intact images and 30 damaged images were selected, equally divided between numerical and experimental. In this case we were unable to obtain an accuracy higher than 83.3% in the training validation phase; thus,

we have not been able to predict the behavior of this network. It was decided to test it anyway and evaluate the results. This condition was also analyzed because we wanted to simulate a situation in which few experimental data were obtained and, therefore, it was necessary to thicken the latter with data obtained numerically. The results confirmed our expectations regarding the incorrect functioning of the digital neural network, producing a very high number of false alarms (109).

Real Classification	undamaged	13	109
	damaged	0	205
		undamaged	damaged
		Predicted Classification	

Fig. 23. Results obtained by the Net trained on numerical results

Given the bad results received from the network trained with numerical data, we no longer trusted it and concentrated only on the other two networks, experimental and hybrid. The “experimental network” also confirmed expectations: it managed to obtain very high recognition percentages, in fact it managed to correctly recognize all the intact images and it managed to recognize about 84% of damaged images.

Real Classification	undamaged	122	0
	damaged	32	173
		undamaged	damaged
		Predicted Classification	

Fig. 24. Results obtained by the Net trained on experimental results

Surprising results were provided by the hybrid network, trained with mixed signals. In fact, overall, it is the network that has shown a higher recognition rate. These results confirmed the high potential that characterizes the hybrid training obtained by combining validated experimental and numerical data.

Real Classification	undamaged	117	5
	damaged	1	204
		undamaged	damaged
		Predicted Classification	

Fig. 25. Results obtained by the Net trained on “hybrid” results

5. CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results showed the concrete possibility of implementing deep learning algorithms for the identification of damage in composite panels. The aim of the work was to develop deep learning algorithms for the classification of guided waves signals aimed to automatize the "multi-path analysis" for damage identification and localization. In particular, starting from a numerical model for Lamb waves simulation in a composite panel, signals relating to an intact and damaged configuration of the panel were obtained, considering four different positions of the damage. The intact and damaged signals, referring to the same path, were then transformed into RGB images each characterized by a well-defined damage index "DI". The images, divided into intact and damaged, were used to train and test a "GoogleNet" convolutional neural network. The network has proved capabilities to correctly classify most of the images (475) while only a small part of them (49) would require an operator intervention to be correctly classified. To further improve the network's ability a larger image dataset, related to both numerical and experimental data, will be used in next future, as well as considering more damaged configurations. For example, the size and shape of the damage could be varied to obtain a network capable of small damage identification and to follow their evolution. Finally it was chosen to carry out three different training approaches of the net, employing only numerical signals, only experimental signals (acquired on the test article numerically correlated) and a combination of them: the results provided were particularly promising for the network trained by the combination of numerical and experimental signals. Further work will be carried out in the next future to better investigate this latter aspects.

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